

The questionnaire was originally developed, validated, and applied in Spanish. For clarity, table headings and notes have been translated into English; the original data remain in Spanish.

Validity Analysis – Dimension 1

Total Variance Explained – Pedagogical Practices, Dimension 1: UDL Principle – Multiple Means of Engagement

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Sums of Squared Loadings of Extraction			Sums of Squared Loadings of Rotation		
	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %
1	6,400	49,227	49,227	6,400	49,227	49,227	3,907	30,056	30,056
2	1,251	9,620	58,847	1,251	9,620	58,847	3,743	28,791	58,847
3	,964	7,415	66,262						
4	,794	6,104	72,367						
5	,650	4,998	77,365						
6	,566	4,355	81,720						
7	,521	4,010	85,730						
8	,438	3,373	89,103						
9	,402	3,095	92,198						
10	,324	2,491	94,689						
11	,287	2,210	96,899						
12	,210	1,614	98,513						
13	,193	1,487	100,000						

Source: Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) Dimension 1 (Own elaboration)

Rotated Factor Matrix – Dimension 1

Rotated Factor Matrix – 1st Dimension of the Questionnaire: UDL Principle – Multiple Means of Engagement		
	Factor 1	Factor 2
C8. I foster a sense of belonging to the community	,860	,074
C13. I foster empathetic and meaningful interpersonal relationships with my students.	,765	,175
C11. I establish behavioral guidelines and conflict-resolution methods agreed upon with the group	,725	,319
C9. I provide consistent and in-depth feedback on my students' performance using instruments based on measurable indicators.	,695	,287
C7. I promote peer collaboration and collective learning	,592	,408
C12. I promote strategies for emotional self-regulation and both group and individual reflection in students.	,549	,522

C6. I facilitate strategies or procedures to scaffold and optimize learning challenges.	,502	,628
C2. I provide various options to motivate learning, taking into account my students' creativity, identity, and interests.	,161	,841
C1. I promote freedom of choice and autonomous work	,044	,730
C5. I maintain effort and consistency by modeling and scaffolding learning objectives, activities, and achievement indicators according to my students' characteristics	,246	,632
C10. I identify my students' expectations, beliefs, and motivations.	,448	,667
C4. I address biases and minimize threats and distractions in the classroom	,446	,578
C3. I encourage play and a respectful learning environment.	,425	,519
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.		
a. Rotation has converged in 3 iterations.		

Source: Rotated Component Analysis – Dimension 1 (Own elaboration)

Validity Analysis – Dimension 2

Total Variance Explained – Pedagogical Practices, Dimension 2: UDL Principle – Multiple Means of Representation

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Sums of Squared Loadings of Extraction			Sums of Squared Loadings of Rotation		
	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %
1	5,866	48,881	48,881	5,866	48,881	48,881	3,607	30,055	30,055
2	1,104	9,200	58,080	1,104	9,200	58,080	3,363	28,026	58,080
3	,876	7,304	65,384						
4	,832	6,936	72,321						
5	,703	5,861	78,182						
6	,571	4,759	82,941						
7	,529	4,406	87,347						
8	,452	3,768	91,115						
9	,396	3,298	94,413						
10	,297	2,473	96,886						
11	,231	1,927	98,813						
12	,142	1,187	100,000						

Source: Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) – Dimension 2 (Own elaboration)

Rotated Factor Matrix – Dimension 2

Rotated Factor Matrix – 2nd Dimension of the Questionnaire: UDL Principle – Multiple Means of Representation		
	Factor 1	Factor 2
R22. I develop new knowledge by connecting it with my students' prior learning.	,570	,487
R19. I promote understanding of and respect for languages and cultural differences.	,833	-,003
R20. I address biases in the use of language and symbols to ensure proper access to information.	,777	,251
R21. I illustrate information in various media of representation according to the learning paces and styles of my students.	,687	,407
R23. I illustrate patterns, characteristics, main ideas, and relationships within knowledge.	,654	,400
R17. I frequently clarify the vocabulary, symbols, and linguistic structure of the materials or instructional resources.	628,	,376
R15. I design personalized and innovative learning experiences with the support of ICT, creating manipulable or interactive materials that facilitate students' perception of information.	,014	,781
R25. I create challenging learning situations that enable students to apply and transfer information to other contexts.	,389	,662
R14. I use the whiteboard and adapt the information in textbooks and written materials to facilitate perception and understanding	,223	,664
R18. I use additional educational resources to support the understanding of texts, mathematical notations, and symbols.	,275	,632
R24. I develop active methodologies that enable the assignment of new meanings to knowledge	,479	,588
R16. The selected educational materials consider diverse perspectives, identities, and cultures	,431	602

Source: Rotated Component Analysis – Dimension 2 (Own elaboration)

Validity Analysis – Dimension 3

Total Variance Explained – 3rd Dimension: Pedagogical Practices, UDL Principle – Multiple Means of Action and Expression

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Sums of Squared Loadings of Extraction			Sums of Squared Loadings of Rotation		
	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %	Total	% de variance	Cumulative %
1	5,713	51,934	51,934	5,257	47,787	47,787	3,809	34,626	34,626
2	1,379	12,535	64,469	0,987	8,973	56,760	2,435	22,134	56,760
3	0,760	6,906	71,374						
4	0,676	6,142	77,516						
5	0,585	5,316	82,833						
6	0,532	4,839	87,671						
7	0,380	3,451	91,122						
8	0,322	2,924	94,046						
9	0,261	2,375	96,421						
10	0,248	2,253	98,674						
11	0,146	1,326	100,000						

Source: Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) – Dimension 3 (Own elaboration)

Rotated Factor Matrix – Dimension 3

Rotated Factor Matrix – 3rd Dimension of the Questionnaire: UDL Principle – Multiple Means of Action and Expression		
	Factor 1	Factor 2
A33. I develop strategies to plan objectives and anticipate challenges.	,882	,148
A32. I establish meaningful objectives according to my students' interests and competencies.	,849	,181
A35. I effectively monitor my students' learning progress.	,830	,100
A34. I organize information and resources to optimize learning.	,774	,232
A36. I reflect critically and inclusively on my teaching practices.	,686	,326
A30. I gradually develop students' skills through practical learning activities.	,631	,553
A26. I diversify assessment and interaction methods through concept maps, collaborative work, gamification, among others.	,105	,819

A29. I facilitate various tools for the construction of creative knowledge through platforms and interactive applications such as Canva or Kahoot, Project- or Problem-Based Learning, creative writing, and Art or design projects.	,240	,772
A27. I provide access to materials, technologies, and assistive tools to interact during learning.	,199	,750
A28. I establish diverse forms of expression and communication of learning, such as verbal, written, graphic, exams, debates, among others.	,561	,474
A31. I addressed biases in the modes of expression and communication of learning.	,548	,356

Source: Rotated Component Analysis – Dimension 3 (Own elaboration)

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Sums of Squared Loadings of Extraction			Sums of Squared Loadings of Rotation		
	Total	% de varianza	% acumulado	Total	% de varianza	% acumulado	Total	% de varianza	% acumulado
1	15,723	43,675	43,675	15,244	42,346	42,346	14,083		
2	1,998	5,551	49,225	1,501	4,169	46,515	6,749		
3	1,724	4,788	54,013	1,230	3,418	49,932	8,743		
4	1,614	4,483	58,496						
5	1,379	3,832	62,328						
6	1,268	3,522	65,849						
7	1,101	3,059	68,909						
8	,939	2,608	71,516						
9	,881	2,447	73,964						
10	,858	2,384	76,348						
11	,826	2,296	78,643						
12	,737	2,047	80,690						
13	,699	1,942	82,633						
14	,654	1,817	84,450						
15	,562	1,561	86,011						
16	,520	1,444	87,455						
17	,479	1,331	88,786						
18	,447	1,242	90,028						
19	,389	1,081	91,109						
20	,378	1,049	92,158						
21	,363	1,009	93,167						
22	,337	,936	94,103						
23	,312	,868	94,971						
24	,240	,667	95,638						
25	,208	,578	96,217						
26	,191	,531	96,747						
27	,182	,505	97,252						
28	,165	,458	97,710						
29	,142	,394	98,104						
30	,131	,365	98,469						
31	,121	,337	98,806						
32	,108	,299	99,105						
33	,105	,291	99,396						
34	,087	,242	99,638						
35	,077	,215	99,853						
36	,053	,147	100,000						

Source: Total Variance Explained – Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) (Own elaboration)